

A FEMINIST ANALYSIS OF THE CHARACTER WIFE IN THE SHORT STORY OF "ANOR" ("THE POMEGRANATE") BY ABDULLA QAHHOR

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Abstract

This paper presents a feminist literary analysis of the wife's character in Abdulla Qahhor's short story *Anor* (*The Pomegranate*). Many interpretations describe the story mainly as a picture of poverty and social hardship. This study challenges that view. Using materialist feminist theory, it argues that the wife's suffering is gender-based, not only economic. The analysis uses close reading to examine characterization, the domestic setting, plot development, narrative point of view, and literary devices such as symbolism, metaphor, irony, and foreshadowing. These elements show that the wife is a marginalized and silenced figure. Special attention is given to her pregnancy, which makes her more vulnerable, and her desire for pomegranates becomes a symbol of denied bodily needs. The study shows that verbal, emotional, and physical violence work together as forms of patriarchal control. As a result, "provision" is presented ironically as something achieved through force. By focusing on the wife's experience, this paper rereads *Anor* as a subtle critique of patriarchal marriage and adds to feminist readings of Uzbek realist literature.

Keywords

Patriarchy; gender and poverty; domestic violence; symbolism; Abdulla Qahhor; *Anor* (*The Pomegranate*)

Introduction

Uzbek prose of the early twentieth century often shows the effects of poverty, tradition, and strict social order, especially in marriage. One writer who presents these issues with strong psychological detail is Abdulla Qahhor. His short story *Anor* (*The Pomegranate*, 1936) is usually read as a realistic story about economic hardship and moral struggle among poor people. However, these readings mostly focus on material conditions and pay little attention to gender relations inside the family.

In *Anor*, poverty affects both the husband and the wife, but they do not experience it in the same way. At first, the husband appears to suffer more because he works hard to earn money. The wife is often expected to be patient and understanding. However, the story shows that the wife, who is never given a name, carries a different burden. She is limited to unpaid housework, emotional endurance, and silence. Her pregnancy makes her more vulnerable. Because she depends on her husband for survival, even small personal needs become controlled and judged. Her desire for pomegranates is not simple or childish. Instead, it reveals how patriarchal power controls women's needs, speech, and bodies within marriage.

This paper uses a feminist literary approach, mainly materialist feminist theory, to study how gendered power works in *Anor*. Rather than seeing the story only as a picture of poverty, the study places the wife's experience at the center. It shows how patriarchy appears through economic control, verbal humiliation, emotional silence, and finally physical violence. The

analysis also examines how narrative elements such as characterization, symbolism, plot development, and narrative point of view help to marginalize the wife.

The study has two main objectives. The first is to examine how patriarchal authority in marriage is created and maintained through economic dependence, language, and violence in the portrayal of the wife in *Anor*. The second is to analyze how the pomegranate works as a symbol of denied female bodily need in a context of poverty and pregnancy. These aims are addressed through two research questions: how does *Anor* show patriarchal power in marriage through the wife's economic dependence and exposure to violence, and how does the pomegranate symbolize the control of female desire and the pregnant body in the story?

Literature Review

Studies of Abdulla Qahhor's *Anor* in Uzbek literary criticism have mainly focused on poverty, social inequality, and moral tension in pre-Soviet society. For example, Qayumova (2024) interprets the story as a realistic depiction of material deprivation and ethical struggle among the poor, with particular attention to the character of Turobjon. In this reading, *Anor* is praised for its concise style, symbolic language, and social realism, qualities that establish Qahhor as a writer of psychological prose (Qayumova, M. 2024).

Qayumova (2024) also explains the conflict between husband and wife mainly as a result of economic hardship. From this perspective, marital tension is treated as a social consequence of poverty rather than a product of unequal gender relations. As a result, the wife appears largely as a secondary figure whose reactions are shaped by material conditions, not as a character subjected to systematic oppression.

Although Qayumova (2024) briefly notes the wife's emotional state—her tears, silence, and psychological breakdown—these features are interpreted as natural responses to poverty and marital stress. Her suffering is therefore normalized and explained through economic difficulty, while the patriarchal structure that limits her voice and power remains unexamined.

At the same time, Qayumova (2024) suggests that Qahhor's prose allows symbolic and psychological interpretations beyond economic explanation. Female characters are described as figures of endurance and moral sensitivity. However, this discussion does not develop a feminist framework or engage with concepts such as female agency, silencing, or domestic patriarchy.

Therefore, despite existing critical attention to *Anor*, there remains a clear gap in feminist literary analysis of the wife's character. Previous studies do not treat her as the main subject of analysis or examine how gendered power structures shape her lived experience. This paper addresses that gap by applying a feminist perspective to the wife's character and by showing how *Anor* exposes the emotional and psychological cost of patriarchal marriage beyond economic hardship.

Methodology

This study uses a qualitative textual analysis based on close reading of **Abdulla Qahhor's** short story *Anor*. The approach is interpretative rather than empirical and focuses on how gendered power relations are shown through narrative details, dialogue, and character interaction. Feminist literary criticism, especially materialist feminist ideas, guides the analysis, but only concepts that directly explain the wife's position in the story are used.

The analysis centers on passages that involve the wife, particularly scenes of domestic labor, verbal interaction between husband and wife, emotional reactions, and moments of

silence. These scenes are selected because they clearly reveal patterns of control, marginalization, and psychological pressure within marriage. Attention is paid to narrative voice, descriptive language, plot development, and the distribution of speech between male and female characters.

Materialist feminist concepts are applied directly to the text. Economic dependence is examined through references to unpaid domestic labor, lack of income, and control over food and consumption. The wife's work inside the home—such as grinding grain, cooking, and maintaining the household—is analyzed as essential but undervalued labor that limits her independence. Her dependence on her husband is shown to restrict even small personal choices, reinforcing her subordinate position.

The study also analyzes patriarchal authority through language. Verbal control is examined by closely reading dismissive expressions, humiliating remarks, and commands used by Turobjon. These speech patterns are treated as forms of psychological pressure that silence the wife and weaken her emotional position. Moments of the wife's silence are not interpreted as agreement or passivity, but as signs of exhaustion and loss of agency within an unequal power relationship.

Another focus of the analysis is denied agency. The wife's desire for pomegranates is examined as a modest but meaningful expression of personal need. The repeated rejection of this desire shows how patriarchal control operates in everyday life, turning minor needs into sources of conflict, shame, and humiliation.

All quotations used in the analysis are translated into English for clarity, with the original Uzbek text provided in parentheses to maintain linguistic accuracy.

Feminist Analysis of the Wife in *Anor (The Pomegranate)*

In *Anor*, the wife is never given a personal name. She is referred to only as “*xotin*” (wife). This immediately limits her identity to marriage and domestic duty. From a feminist perspective, namelessness shows how a woman's individuality is erased under patriarchy. She exists only in relation to her husband, not as an independent person.

The wife first appears while doing housework. She is grinding maize when her husband enters the house. The text states that “*his wife, who was grinding maize, saw the bundle in his hand*” (“*Jo‘xori tuyayotgan xotini uning qo‘lidagi tugunchani ko‘rib*”). Her labour is shown before her thoughts or emotions. This presents unpaid domestic work as her main function in the story.

Her pregnancy makes her position even more vulnerable. This is made clear when Turobjon accuses her, “*You called the unborn baby a curse*” (“*Hali tug‘ilmagan bolani yer yutkur deding-a*”). The reference to the unborn child connects the wife's suffering to reproductive labour. Instead of care and protection, her pregnant body becomes another site of control. Feminist analysis shows that motherhood under economic dependence increases oppression rather than reducing it.

Poverty affects both husband and wife, but not equally. Turobjon uses money as a tool of authority. He repeats economic calculations to control food and desire, saying, “*Pomegranate, pomegranate... a pound of pomegranates costs so much! ... what I earn in a month is only eighteen tangas*” (“*Anor, anor... Bir qadoq anor falon pul bo‘lsa!... bir oyda oladiganim o‘n sakkiz tanga pul*”). His speech presents him as the rational decision-maker and frames the wife's desire as unreasonable.

The wife speaks not because of selfish desires, but bodily needs. Her cry, *“What kind of curse is this!.. Why don’t I crave flour, salt, a clod of earth like other people?!”* (*“Bu yer yutkur qanday balo ekan!.. Odamlarday gulutaga, tuzga, kesakka boshqorong’i bo’lsam-chi!”*), expresses pent up resentment, and exhaustion. Feminist reading shows that male economic logic is valued, while female need is dismissed, even during pregnancy.

Most of the story takes place inside the house. Feminist criticism sees the domestic space as a key site of control. The house is dark, poor, and lifeless. Food lacks colour and nourishment: *“even yogurt could not give color to the darkened porridge”* (*“Qozonning zangi chiqib qoraygan go’jaga qatig ham rang kirgizolmadi”*). This reflects the wife’s emotional and physical deprivation.

Domestic labour is enforced through commands. When Turobjon tells the wife to sew his coat, his language is harsh: *“Here, sew this - here!”* (*“Ma, buni tik,— dedi u”*). He pressures her further: *“Enough - take it... I’m telling you!”* (*“Bo’l,— dedi... — ol... Senga aytyapman!”*). Feminist analysis identifies this as naturalized exploitation, where women’s labor is expected and unquestioned.

The plot shows a clear escalation of control. It begins with verbal discipline. Turobjon tells her, *“Have cravings, okay, but be reasonable!”* (*“Axir, boshqorong’i bo’l, evida bo’l-da!”*). This language silences her.

When the wife reacts emotionally, the narrator notes that *“she burst out crying loudly”* (*“Xotin turayotib baralla yig’lab yubordi”*). Her emotions are treated as disruption. The turning point comes with the curse, said by Turobjon, *“May your insides be crushed!”* (*“Jigarlaring ezilib ketsin!”*). The narrator adds, *“how those words affected her, only the wife knew”* (*“Bu so’z unga qanday ta’sir qilganini faqat boshqorong’i xotingina biladi”*). Her suffering is recognized but remains isolated and unheard.

Violence follows. The act is described as this: *“He could not tell whether he kicked her shoulder and then stood up, or stood up and then kicked her”* (*“Turobjon bilolmay qoldi: xotining yelkasiga tepib, so’ngra o’rnidan turdimi, yo turib keyin tepdimi”*). The wife’s language collapses into pleading: *“Please... please...”* (*“Qo’ying... Qo’ying...”*). Dialogue ends here and communication becomes physical.

The third-person narrator usually limits access to the wife’s inner thoughts. Feminist narratology links this to the marginalization of female consciousness. However, after the curse, the narrative briefly enters her mind. She realizes her husband has always been emotionally absent: *“it seemed to her this man had been grumbling for three years... today he finally said three words clearly”* (*“nazarida, bu odam shu uch yildan beri g’uldirab kelgan... uch so’zni ravshanroq aytdi”*). That three words being the curse told by Turobjon.

The most important feminist moment follows: *“In the world, the only person she leaned on was her husband; her only dream was the pomegranate—suddenly both were wiped out”* (*“Olamda uning suyangani eri, birdan bir orzusi — anor edi, birdaniga har ikkisi ham yo’qqa chiqdi”*). Patriarchy destroys both emotional security and personal desire at the same time.

The pomegranate symbolizes denied agency and bodily need. The desire is small but constant. In her imagination, their rich neighbor - Mullajon qozi’s garden becomes abundance: *“not a garden, but a pomegranate orchard... pomegranates hanging in clusters, as big as kettles”* (*“bog’ emas, anorzor... Anor daraxtlarida anor shig’il... choynakday-choynakday”*). Desire grows because it is denied.

When pomegranates finally appear, they arrive through violence. Turobjon returns with a bundle, and “*a bedsheet full of pomegranates rolled in every direction*” (“*Bir choyshab anor har tomonga yumalab ketdi*”). Feminist irony lies in the fact that provision comes only after terror.

Irony also exposes the failure of the provider role. Turobjon suggests, “*If that is your longing, then marry someone richer*” (“*Bunday armoning bo’lsa hali ham serpulroq odamga teg*”). The wife responds, “*For two pomegranates you are not ashamed to hand your wife over to a rich man!*” (“*Ikkita anor uchun xotiniigizni serpul odamga oshirgani uyaling!*”). Her resistance is brief and is immediately punished with violence.

Foreshadowing appears in the narrator’s line: “*in moments like these, words refuse to move the tongue; if they do, they do the work of a fist*” (“*Mana shunday vaqtlarda til qotib og’izda aylanmay qoladi, mabodo aylansa, mushtning xizmatini qiladi*”). This clearly shows how verbal control leads to physical abuse. Feminist analysis reads this as proof that domestic violence grows out of everyday linguistic domination, not sudden anger.

Discussion

This feminist analysis reinterprets *Anor* as more than a story about poverty. While earlier studies mainly describe the conflict as a result of economic hardship and class struggle, this study shows that poverty alone cannot explain the wife’s suffering. Instead, poverty works as a condition that allows patriarchal power to operate and grow inside marriage.

Previous criticism, especially studies available through [inLIBRARY](#), often focuses on Abdulla Qahhor’s realism, symbolism, and social themes. These readings usually center on Turobjon as a tragic figure shaped by poverty. In this approach, the wife is seen as a secondary character whose emotional reactions are treated as natural responses to hardship. This study challenges that view by showing that her suffering is not accidental or temporary but shaped by gendered power relations. Materialist feminist analysis explains that although both spouses are poor, only the wife is repeatedly silenced, humiliated, and punished.

The findings also respond to earlier observations that describe the wife as emotionally fragile. The symbolic meaning of the pomegranate is also reconsidered. Earlier interpretations often treat it as a symbol of unattainable wealth or moral temptation. This study offers a different reading. From a feminist perspective, the pomegranate represents denied female agency and bodily need, especially during pregnancy. The refusal to meet this small desire is not only about money. It is a way of controlling the wife’s body and disciplining her desire within marriage. The discussion further shows that violence in *Anor* develops gradually. Verbal control comes first, then humiliation, and finally physical force. The narrator’s line about words doing “the work of a fist” supports feminist arguments that domestic violence grows out of everyday language. This challenges interpretations that treat the final act of violence as sudden or emotional. Instead, it appears as the result of everyday patriarchal control.

Conclusion

This study has reread *Anor (The Pomegranate)* from a feminist perspective. The story is often seen as a realist account of poverty. However, poverty alone does not explain the wife’s suffering. Her pain is shaped by patriarchal power inside marriage. Economic hardship becomes a tool of control and that limits her choices, silences her voice, justifying violence.

Using materialist feminist ideas, this study showed that the wife’s unpaid domestic labour and economic dependence place her in a weak position. Her pregnancy increases this vulnerability instead of bringing care or protection. Her desire for pomegranates is small, but

meaningful, representing bodily need, dignity, and personal agency. This desire is denied and judged and when finally, the pomegranates appear, they come after fear and violence. This shows the irony of patriarchal “provision.” The analysis highlights how narrative choices such as the domestic setting, silence, symbolism, and foreshadowing reveal that violence grows from everyday verbal control, showing that *Anor* critiques patriarchal marriage rather than only poverty in Abdulla Qahhor’s prose.

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